

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF CULTURAL SPECIFIC VOCABULARY OF WEDDING IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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It is generally accepted in modern linguistics that language is a mirror of culture, that it is a reflection of the whole being, and that it reflects the worldview. Each language contains all the features that characterize the nation to which it belongs, the members of society who use it, and on this basis, languages, and nations are separated from each other. Language in the form of oral and written speech collects, preserves, and transmits to the next generation samples of lexicon, phraseology, grammar, fiction of the cultural and spiritual riches of the people. In the process of learning the language, especially the natural language, the student learns the rich cultural heritage and spiritual values that are passed down from generation to generation. Along with textbooks, the role of various school dictionaries, information banks, lexical minimums are important in this process. Dictionaries are the most ancient form of linguistic sources. They have a purely practical purpose - to clarify and explain the meaning of obscure words used in speech.

Etymological method is the first step in the analysis of the concept. It enables to obtain necessary knowledge on the original meaning of the concept. For the English linguculturology, the notion “wedding” has the following etymological meanings: “to pledge”, “to engage, wed”, being a French word its original form was as “weddung, weddian”, afterwards addition “-ing” formed today’s modern for “wedding”¹, as for Uzbek “toy” is an ancient Turkic word that is “wedding” in English, has a preliminary form “to’q” later formed into “toy” because of assimilation meant “to satisfy the

¹ Klein E. A comprehensive etymological dictionary of the English Language:AE Netherlands,Amsterdam, Elsevier Science. 1979

hunger” and “to occupy a space”². Descriptive method provided explanation on the meaning of “wedding”. According to Merriam-Webster English explanatory dictionary “wedding” has some meanings:

- 1) a marriage ceremony usually with its accompanying festivities;
- 2) an act, process, or instance of joining in close association;

3) a wedding anniversary or its celebration-usually used in combination: a golden wedding. National Uzbek Encyclopedia gives the following definition for the word “toy”: “a custom organized with banquet, celebration and merriments”. Explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language gives the following definition: “Toy (wedding) is a party or celebration organized and realized among people on the reason of marrying one’s children”. Finally, selection of English and Uzbek proverbs, idioms about wedding tradition presented an opportunity to use comparative-typological method and find out cultural specific features of this concept. Dictionary of proverbs and idioms in both languages are the basic sources of our research. We carried out analysis of wedding and pointed out similar, unique, common peculiarities of the concept. In most phraseological units, attitude of people towards a wedding is described with the elements of joy, excitement, expectations. For example, an English idiom big day is used to say about the Wedding Day among people and figurative meaning of the idiom depicts that this day is highly important and crucial for the English people. It is believed that wedding brings happiness not only for the heroes of it, but also other people, such as guests, friends, relatives of a bride and a groom. The following proverb can be example for it: One wedding brings another³ so at a wedding party people can meet his or her future spouse and decide to get married as the English proverbs says: Hanging and wedding go by destiny. Similarly, the Uzbek expect a wedding day, and in no case they postpone or delay it, even if financial or other factors exist.

² Rahmatullayev Sh. O’zbek tilining etimologik lug’ati. Etymological Dictionary of the Uzbek language, Tashkent, V. 2009.

³ Martin H. Manser. The Facts on File Dictionary of Proverbs, New York, Infobase Publishing, 2007.

The proverb *Atala bo'lsa ham to'y bo'lsin* (Let a wedding be, even though wedding dish is *Atala*). “*Atala*” is an Uzbek easily and fast prepared liquid dish and not requiring expensive and many ingredients

. I. Weddings. The colour “white” in the phrase “White wedding” symbolizes an English bride’s dress and the marriage that starts in a church. Cambridge dictionary describes it as following: “a traditional Christian marriage in a church, at which the woman who is getting married wears a white dress”. As for Uzbek traditions, people organize following weddings: *O'g'il to'yi* (a wedding organized to celebrate a boy’s circumcision), *hovli to'yi* (celebrities organized when a family moves in a new house) and the most important wedding for a family is *nikoh to'yi* (wedding of a bride and a groom).

II. Pre - wedding rituals, traditions:

a) Choosing wedding date. English proverb *Marry in May, rue for aye* describes the English people cautious in deciding a suitable month for their wedding.

b) Preparation of wedding clothes. English rituals related to a bride such as something new, something old, something borrowed, and something blue is considered to be must-follow rule concerning a bride’s wedding outlook in advance. And these are the symbols of a future, happy life for a new married couple. Such examples of pre-wedding rituals, customs were revealed only in the English language materials.

Wedding preparations of Uzbek people are reflected in the followings cases:

a) Consulting about wedding organization. Uzbek proverbs *Kengashli tuy tarqamas* (Wedding organized with Council will not be ruined); *Tuy kengash bilan bo'lur* (Wedding should be organized with council). According to these proverbs, a family organizing a wedding for their child must consult with relatives, neighbours, take recommendations from friends who have a proper life experience on it.

b) Pre-wedding event. A ritual mostly specific for Asian people is to organize so called *Maslahat oshi* (Arrangement pilaf) to arrange about all the necessary things for a wedding event, all close relatives, friends, neighbor gather in the house of the host of the wedding event, prepare national Uzbek meal “*Pilaf*” and consulting process is

carried out over eating this meal and after too. So, pilaf here is presented as a realia and symbolizes solidarity of Uzbek people in organizing big events such as wedding party. Similar examples were not found in the English language materials.

III. Wedding Day.

a) Wedding dishes. An Uzbek wedding day begins with “Nahorgi osh”, “To’y ochi” (Wedding pilaf) early in the morning. A bride’s parents prepare a great amount of pilaf and invite guests to taste it and pray for the happiness of newlyweds. In the event “Nahorgi osh”, both chefs who prepare a lot of pilaf, guests and hosts make up it very joyful and interesting since they, talk, dance and listen to songs. The description of this event is reflected in the following Uzbek proverb: Tuy oshi to’polon oshi (Wedding pilaf is a fuss pilaf). Resembling ritual can be noticed in English called “Wedding breakfast”. However, wedding breakfast, unlike Uzbek “Nahorgi osh”, is served after wedding and only for newly-weds. Wedding cake is served during wedding breakfas or wedding reception, as a rule. It is prepared and is eaten as a symbol of sweet, tasty life of a bride and groom. A number of sources define wedding cake as following: “Traditionally, wedding cakes were made to bring good luck to all guests and the couple”.

b) Wedding ceremony. The idiom give someone away means to accompany a bride to the place a groom waits for in a church. This process is full of emotional moments both for bride and group and their relatives also. The action figuratively described in the idiom explains that a close person of a bride present her to a groom. Another English wedding tradition is first dance which is carried out by a bride and a groom for the first time after they get married. The music of the dance, as a rule is choosed by the couple and is usually a music with a slow temp. Uzbek bride leaves her parents’house under the song “Yor-Yor” the following definition for “Yor-Yor” is provided: “The context of the song that is sung when a bride is taken to a groom’s house introduces a bride to the groom and groom is introduced to the bride, feelings, emotions of a bride is delivered by the song” is an Uzbek realia representing a symbolical farewell song with her parents of a bride. A team of men (groom and his

friends) that is “kuyov navkar” visit the bride’s house. Young men for kuyov navkar are chosen according to their marital status and age, they are mostly married men and usually older than a groom. They are invited to the living-room where is a big table filled with different meals and sweetsto have a small party until the bride’s friends prepare her to present to the groom. Then, the groom and the bride get blessing and permission from the bride’s parent and leave the bride’s house together with kuyov navkar. The mission of kuyov navkar is to support a groom emotionally on such an exiting day for him.

c) Greetings and wishes on a wedding day. Guests that come to congratulate a bride and a groom in English weddings express their wishes with huge emotions: “...wheat is thrown over the bridal couple with the cry "Bread for life and pudding forever," expressive of a wish that the newly wed may be always affluent. The throwing of rice, a very ancient custom but one later than the wheat is symbolical of the wish that the bridal may be fruitful. The most famous Uzbek greeting reflected in the idiom is uttered for a newly-wed is “Kushganing bilan kusha kari” (Get older together) expresses a strong wish of relatives and friends of the couple to live forever together as one family.

VI. Post-wedding activities. After wedding comes “Wedding Reception” and it is a small party organized to let a bride and a groom be hosts for the first time after they are married. “...an English reception features an elaborate fruitcake made from cherries, ground nuts, and other sweet ingredients. Concerning Uzbek post-wedding rituals, a bride gets acquainted with the groom’s relatives and vise versa. A ritual called “Kelin salom” (Bride’s greetings) is carried out after the first day of the wedding or in the evening on a wedding day. The bride wears national Uzbek costumes, makes her face invisible with handkerchief and bents to greet each member of a groom’s family under the tunes of song “Kelin salom”, after “Kelin salom” come another ritual “Bet ochar” (Face opening) when a bride takes away a handkerchief from her face and let other to see her face. After three days or in a week, a bride’s parents invite a groom and his family for a party “Challar” (Calling) organized for in-laws. At the party

relatives, parents of a bride and a groom talk, get acquainted with each other more closely, eat, during, sing songs and dance. It is seen from provided examples that wedding tradition is specific for both linguocultures. The results of the analysis show that specific feature of wedding tradition and its rituals make up 90%, whereas similarities 10 % that is special wedding dishes “wedding cake” for English, and “Nahorgi osh” for Uzbek and the ritual of expressing wishes and greetings for newly-wed. The reason can be explained by the fact that English and Uzbek relate to different language families first of all, secondly mentality, life experience, geographical position, religion that strongly differ from one another.

Both English and Uzbek wedding traditions possess considerable systemic potentials. In English lexical system there fixed associations such as “wedding preparations”, “importance of wedding cake, dance” and after wedding activities. In phraseological level, the notion wedding tradition includes a number of specific elements that was not revealed in the Uzbek linguoculturology: choosing an appropriate wedding date, paying attention to the symbolic elements in a bride’s dress and to accompany a bride in a church. For Uzbek, lexical level of wedding tradition is associated with rituals carried out on a wedding day and post-wedding ritual, phraseological level includes prewedding rituals. Analysis show that wedding tradition is inherent for both linguocultures, however we reveled more dissimilar unique features of it rather than similar. Importance of the availability of specifically prepared wedding dishes, guests’ wishes and greetings addressed for newly-weds were found out similar feature of wedding traditions reflected in the languages.

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